

TO COMPARE THE FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF CLOSED REDUCTION AND PLASTER OF PARIS APPLICATION WITH CLOSED REDUCTION AND K-WIRE FIXATION AND PLASTER OF PARIS APPLICATION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF COLLE'S FRACTURE

Dr. Suqlain Ali¹, Dr. Tanveer Haider², Dr. Omer Farooq³, Dr. Abdul Hannan⁴,
Dr. Furqan Mudassar⁵, Dr. Junaid Iqbal⁶

¹PGR FCPS Orthopedic Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot.

^{2,4}Associate Professor of Orthopedic Surgery, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.

³Assistant Professor of Orthopedic Surgery, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.

⁵PGR Orthopedic Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot.

⁶PGR Orthopedic Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot.

¹maliksaqlainali@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Suqlain Ali

Abstract

Objective:

To compare the functional outcomes of closed reduction and Plaster of Paris cast application versus closed reduction, K-wire fixation and Plaster of Paris cast application in the management of Colle's fractures.

Methodology:

This randomized control trial was conducted at Department of Orthopedic Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot / Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College Sialkot from 06-March-2025 to 06-June-2025. Total 60 patients (30 in each group) were included in the study. Patients were randomly divided into two groups with through online randomization calculator. Patients in Group-A were treated with close reduction and cast application while patients in Group-B were treated with close reeducation with K-wire fixation. The casts and K-wires were removed after six weeks. Final follow-up was done at three months, and the Gartland and Werley score was calculated for both groups

Results: Significantly higher proportion of excellent (30%) and good (33.30%) outcomes were in Group-B compared to Group-A (closed reduction with cast application). Conversely, fair (36.70%) and poor (26.70%) outcomes were more frequently observed in Group-A, reflecting comparatively inferior functional recovery. i.e. p-value=0.122. Age and gender had no significant impact on functional outcome of both treatment modalities.

Conclusion: This results of this study suggests that, at 3 months post-treatment, K-wire fixation provides improved stability and facilitates better functional recovery, supporting its use as a preferred technique for managing Colles' fractures although the difference was not statistically significant.

Introduction

The distal radius fractures present a treatment challenge, especially when high-energy trauma and intra-articular involvement and

comminution are present. Misalignment of the extra-articular joints can lead to decreased grip strength, limited motion and carpal instability. Depending on the fracture pattern, various

therapeutic procedures such as close reduction, percutaneous pin fixation, and external and internal fixation have yielded different results¹.² Unstable radial metaphysis bending fractures such as Colle's fractures, are mostly treated by open reduction and internal fixation to maintain palmar tilt, minimize collapse, and avoid radio-carpal joint bridge although there are no clear guidelines for management. Percutaneous K-wire fixation has also been used to offer additional stability.^{3, 4} Conservative management using closed reduction and Plaster of Paris application is also a valid option. Raza et al. compared the outcomes of conservative therapy (plaster of Paris cast) with a K-wire fixation for closed, isolated distal radius fractures. The union rate for conservative therapy was 95.7% and 96% for K-wire fixation. Group A had 70% of patients with excellent, 20% with good, 6% with average, and 4% with poor outcomes. In Group B, 80% had excellent, 8% with good, 8% average, and 4% had poor outcomes. Hence both methods were statistically significant efficient in treating Colles' fracture.⁵ Nikunj et al. included 50 adult patients with Colles' fracture into two groups i.e., plaster cast and K-wire plus plaster cast. After 6 months, 10% of patients in Group A had excellent, 24% good, 12% average, and 4% had poor outcomes. In Group B, 10% of patients had excellent, 26% good, 14% average, and none had bad outcomes producing comparable results⁶. Colle's fracture Conservative management using plaster casts has proven to be a highly effective treatment approach, yielding favorable outcomes in both functional recovery and anatomical alignment⁷. However, documented clinical trials directly comparing different treatment regimens are scarce. The rationale of this study is to compare the functional outcome of closed reduction and plaster cast application and closed reduction and k wire fixation in the management of Colle's fracture and to promote closed reduction and plaster cast application as it is cheap, less time consuming, no indoor admission is required and can be done in local anesthesia and suits the over burden tertiary care hospitals in developing countries like ours.

Methodology:

This randomized control trial was conducted at Department of Orthopedic Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot / Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College Sialkot from 06-March-2025 to 06-June-2025. Ethical approval was taken from Institutional research board. A total of 60 patients (30 in each group) were included based on 80% power of test, 5% level of significance, and expected excellent functional result rates of 90%⁶ in the conservative (POP) group and 36%⁶ in the K-wire fixation group. Inclusion criteria for patients was patients aged 18-60 years either gender presenting with Colle's fracture (distal 2.5 cm of radius diagnosed radiologically on x rays) with injury duration <1 week. However, patients presenting with open fracture, fracture with neuro vascular injury and patients medically unfit for surgery by a consultant orthopedic surgeon and consultant anesthesiologist. Patients recruitment was done with non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Informed consent was taken from all patients. The basic demographic information, such as name, age, gender, fracture duration, and fracture side (left/right), was recorded. Using online randomization calculator, patients were divided into two equal groups of 72 individuals each. A single surgical team performed all procedures following standard operating protocols. In Group A, patients, after being given the hematoma block with local anaesthesia, had their fractures reduced by the longitudinal radial traction and counter-traction method, along with ulnar deviation and manipulation of distal fracture fragments, and a POP cast was applied. In Group B, patients, after being given general anaesthesia, had their fractures reduced by the traction and counter-traction method, along with manipulation of distal fracture fragments. After closed reduction, the fracture fixation was done with percutaneous K-wire under image intensifier, and a POP cast was applied. Immediate post-reduction radiographs were taken to confirm fracture reduction and to identify any displacement. Group A patients were discharged on the same day, and Group B patients were discharged the next day with instructions for plaster of Paris (POP) treatment, including active finger, elbow, and shoulder

exercises. Follow-up appointments were made in the second and sixth weeks. The casts and K-wires were removed after six weeks. As part of the therapeutic approach, physiotherapy was advised. Final follow-up was done at three months, and the Gartland and Werley score (0-2: Excellent, 3-8: Good, 9-20: Fair and ≥ 21 : Poor) was calculated for both groups.

Data entry and analysis was carried out with Statistical Packages for social sciences (SPSS) version 25. Quantitative data was presented with Mean \pm SD and qualitative data with frequency and percentage. Normality of quantitative variables were test through Kolmogorov Smirnov test. Quantitative parameters (age, duration of fracture and Gartland and Werley Score) were compared between groups with Mann Whitney u test. Functional outcome was compared between groups with Chi Square test. Effect modifiers (Age and Gender) were controlled through stratification. Post stratification Chi square test was applied to see the impact of effect modifiers on final outcome. Statistical significance was set as p-value ≤ 0.05 .

Results:

There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups regarding age, duration of fracture, gender distribution, or affected side. This indicates that the baseline characteristics were comparable and balanced across both treatment modalities, ensuring that outcome differences are not attributable to demographic

variability (Table-I) The graphical representation shows a higher proportion of excellent and good outcomes in Group-B (closed reduction with percutaneous K-wire fixation) compared to Group-A (closed reduction with cast application). Conversely, fair and poor outcomes were more frequently observed in Group-A, reflecting comparatively inferior functional recovery. (Figure-I) In patients aged 20-40 years, Group-B demonstrated a higher proportion of excellent and good outcomes, with fewer fair or poor results, whereas Group-A showed a higher proportion of fair and poor outcomes. Among patients aged 41-60 years, functional outcomes were relatively similar between the groups, although Group-B still showed a slight advantage. In patients over 60 years, Group-B again demonstrated more favorable outcomes, with fewer poor results. However, none of these differences reached statistical significance (p-value > 0.05) (Table-II) When stratified by gender, both males and females in Group-B demonstrated a higher frequency of excellent and good outcomes compared to Group-A. Similarly, for the affected side, patients with left-sided fractures treated with K-wire fixation (Group-B) achieved superior functional outcomes compared to those managed with casting (Group-A). Despite these trends, the differences did not reach statistical significance (p-value > 0.05). (Table-III).

Table-I: Patients Characteristics

		Group-A	Group-B	p-value
		30	30	
Age (Years)	Mean \pm SD	46.26 \pm 19.06	49.26 \pm 15.93	0.363 ^(f)
	Median (IQR)	41(32.25)	45(29.50)	
Duration of Fracture (Days)	Mean \pm SD	4.26 \pm 1.799	3.76 \pm 2.17	0.353 ^(f)
	Median (IQR)	4.50(3.25)	4(5)	
Gender	Male	18(60%)	21(70%)	0.589 ^(c)
	Female	12(40%)	9(30%)	
Effectted Side	Right	21(70%)	15(50%)	0.187 ^(c)
	Left	9(30%)	15(50%)	
Gartland and Werley Score	Mean \pm SD	10.96 \pm 8.08	8.26 \pm 7.09	0.159 ^(f)
	Median (IQR)	10(19)	7(9.25)	

Note: (f) Mann Whitney U test, (c) Chi-Square test
 Group-A:(Closed reduction and cast application)
 Group-B (Closed reduction and percutaneous K-wire fixation)

Figure-1: Functional outcome of patients

Table-II: Functional outcome (Gartland and Werley Score) in relation to patients age

	20-40		41-60		>60	
	Group-A	Group-B	Group-A	Group-B	Group-A	Group-B
Excellent	1(6.7%)	3(33.3%)	1(16.7%)	3(27.3%)	1(11.1%)	3(30%)
Good	4(26.7%)	5(55.6%)	1(16.7%)	2(18.2%)	3(33.3%)	3(30%)
Fair	6(40%)	1(11.1%)	1(16.7%)	5(45.5%)	4(44.4%)	2(20%)
Poor	4(26.7%)	0(0%)	3(50%)	1(9.1%)	1(11.1%)	2(20%)
Total	15	9	6	11	9	10
p-value	0.064 ^(f)		0.388 ^(f)		0.666 ^(f)	

Note: (f) Fisher Exact test

Group-A:(Closed reduction and cast application)

Group-B (Closed reduction and percutaneous K-wire fixation)

Table-III: Functional outcome (Gartland and Werley Score) in relation to patients Gender and effected side

	Gender				Effected Side			
	Male		Female		Right		Left	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Excellent	1(5.6%)	5(23.8%)	2(16.7%)	4(44.4%)	2(9.5%)	3(20%)	1(11.1%)	6(40%)
Good	5(27.8%)	7(33.3%)	3(25%)	3(33.3%)	5(23.8%)	5(33.3%)	3(33.3%)	5(33.3%)
Fair	6(33.3%)	6(28.6%)	5(41.7%)	2(22.2%)	7(33.3%)	5(33.3%)	4(44.4%)	3(20%)
Poor	6(33.3%)	3(14.3%)	2(16.7%)	0(0%)	7(33.3%)	2(13.3%)	1(11.1%)	1(6.7%)
Total	18	21	12	9	21	15	9	15
p-value	0.322		0.425		0.545		0.412	

Note: (f) Fisher Exact test

Group-A:(Closed reduction and cast application)

Group-B (Closed reduction and percutaneous K-wire fixation)

DISCUSSION

The management of Colles fractures through closed reduction and plaster cast application versus closed reduction with K-wire fixation has been subject of comparative studies.⁸ The results of our study revealed trend toward better functional outcomes in patients treated with closed reduction and percutaneous K-wire fixation followed by Plaster of Paris application (Group B) compared to those treated with closed reduction and Plaster of Paris application alone (Group A). Although differences did not reach statistical significance (p -value > 0.05), higher proportion of excellent and good outcomes was observed in Group B, whereas fair and poor outcomes were more frequent in Group A. Similarly, Yadav found that, all patients in cast and K-wire group showed clinical and radiological union at 12 weeks, however, K-wire group was found to be more comfortable, experienced fewer complications, and achieved better functional, and anatomical outcomes compared to cast group.⁹ Adarsh et al, also concluded that both groups showed comparable functional outcomes ($p > 0.05$), indicating no statistically significant difference between cast application alone and K-wire fixation. However, K-wire fixation provided better stability and radiological alignment, helping maintain anatomical reduction more effectively.³ Dinkar et al, also supported current results.¹⁰ Amruth and Anand found that 71.9% patients achieved excellent outcomes, with only minor complications i.e. collapse, stiffness, numbness, and superficial infection observed in few cases, and fracture union occurred in under three months.¹¹ In contrast, Pathuri (2020) emphasize that K-wire fixation, while beneficial for stability, may not be necessary for all patients, particularly in less complex fractures.¹² Across all age groups, patients treated with K-wire fixation (Group B) consistently showed better functional outcomes than those managed with casting alone (Group A); however, these differences were not statistically significant (p -value > 0.05). Both male and female patients, as well as those with left-sided fractures, demonstrated better functional outcomes with K-wire fixation; however, these differences were not statistically

significant (p -value > 0.05). Similarly, there is also no global consensus on optimal treatment approach or the effectiveness related to management across different age groups.¹³ Zhang et al, declared that K-wire fixation is a safe, technique that provides effective treatment option for unstable Colles' fractures in elderly patients.¹⁴ However, Ortona et al, concluded that, males generally exhibit faster or stronger bone healing than females, likely due to differences in hormonal profiles, inflammatory responses, cellular mechanisms, and lifestyle factors. Further experimental and clinical studies are required to clarify the influence of sex and gender on bone healing processes.¹⁵ A trial by Hsueh et al, indicates that elderly females with dorsally comminuted unstable Colles' fractures may benefit from more rigid fixation methods than standard percutaneous K-wire pinning.¹⁶ This study had small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, patients were not followed for a longer duration, preventing assessment of long-term functional and radiological outcomes. Larger studies with extended follow-up are recommended to validate these results.

CONCLUSION

This study suggests that, at 3 months post-treatment, K-wire fixation provides improved stability and facilitates better functional recovery, supporting its use as a preferred technique for managing Colles' fractures as assessed by Gartland and Werley Score, although the difference was not statistically significant.

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